

MASCULINITIES DEFINITIONS

Addendum to the REAL DEAL Gender Glossary

- **Cisgender** - “A term that refers to a person who does not identify as trans, and instead feels aligned with the gender they were assigned at birth.” Learn more: [ILGA Europe](#)
- **Colonialism** - Colonialism is when a country violently takes over another country, and forces its way of life (cultural practices, economic development, language, religious beliefs etc.) on the local and indigenous people. This has created a dynamic whereby the coloniser extracts resources (such as natural resources, wealth, labour) from the colonies in order to further their own development, whilst hindering the development of the colonies. This is the biggest cause of global inequality. For more definitions, check out our [REAL DEAL gender glossary](#).
- **Critical Race Theory** - coined by Kimberlé Williams Crenshaw (who also coined “intersectionality”) and is an academic and legal framework. CRT “recognizes that racism is embedded in laws, policies and institutions that uphold and reproduce racial inequalities. According to CRT, societal issues like Black Americans’ higher mortality rate, outsized exposure to police violence, the school-to-prison pipeline, denial of affordable housing, and the death rates of Black women in childbirth are not unrelated anomalies.” Source: [NAACP LDF](#), further reading: NY Times “[what is critical race theory.](#)” If you are interested in the legal analysis, you can also check out the blog: [criticallegalthinking.com](#)
- **Decolonisation** - The process of highlighting, challenging and undoing colonial structures that persist today. For more definitions, such as “historical responsibilities”, check out our [REAL DEAL gender glossary](#).
- **Eco-fascist masculinity** - actors embodying (far-right) hypermasculinity, who are recognising the climate crisis and arguing that white supremacy and racism is the solution. “Environmentalism through genocide”. Learn more: “[Nature, Masculinities, Care, and the Far-Right](#)”
- **Ecofeminism (modern)** - “an intersectional feminist approach to fighting structural barriers that prevents us from enjoying a healthy environment. These barriers include patriarchy, capitalism, extractivism, militarism, gender-based violence, digital misinformation and shrinking space for civil society to influence. By “intersectional” we recognise that we all come with a different baggage of discrimination (or lack thereof) depending on our gender, age, race, sexual identity, education, religion, ability, socioeconomic status or other identity markers. Learn more: “[Why the European Green Deal Needs Ecofeminism](#)”

- **Ecological masculinities (also “sustainable masculinities”)** - A conceptual and practical framework that questions traditional notions of masculinities that could contribute to environmentally harmful effects. It encourages redefining masculinities to promote more sustainable and eco-friendly attitudes and actions. Source: [Ecological masculinities: Theoretical foundations and practical guidance](#).
- **Ecomodern masculinity** - when people try to make harmful things to the environment seem eco-friendly. For example, when Arnold Schwarzenegger promoted "eco-friendly" Hummer cars. "Ecomodernists" believe there's no problem balancing economic growth with protecting the environment. They think using advanced technologies, often controlled by private businesses, can fix any environmental issue. In the context of masculinity, this could involve portraying eco-friendly behaviours as compatible with traditional expectations of masculinity. To learn more, read: [“The making of an Environmental Hero: The rise of ecological modern discourse, fuel cells and Arnold Schwarzenegger”](#)
- **Environmental racism** - “It is not a coincidence or a geo-physical accident that racialised communities are amongst the hardest hit by the climate crisis, worldwide including in Europe. Often, their disproportionate exposure is a result of interactions between climactic changes and structural racism, resulting in racialised people being denied employment, income, a healthy and safe environment and access to political decision-making.” Source: www.enar-eu.org/about/climate-justice
- **Essentialist / essentialism** - In the early days, when ecofeminism came about as a concept, it was often looked at from a very narrow perspective. Grand assumptions were made that weren't necessarily rooted in our lived intersectional realities. Some claimed that women were more nurturing and thus closer to nature. Their underlying assumption was that no matter where in the world, women experienced the same challenges. This line of thinking fails on several levels as it doesn't recognise the diversity of women and their experiences. It also makes assumptions based on gender roles created by society, rather than tackles them. That's why it's so important that modern ecofeminism has an intersectional analysis. (Source: WECF)
- **Feminist care theory** (also “feminist ‘ethics of care’ theory”) - “Species activity that includes everything that we do to maintain, continue and repair our 'world' so that we can live in it as well as possible. That world includes our bodies, our environments, all of which we seek to interweave in a complex, life-sustaining web.” Learn more: [“Rethinking Care Ethics: On the Promise and Potential of an Intersectional Analysis”](#)
- **Gender betrayal** - refers to the perception or accusation that an individual is betraying the expectations or norms associated with their gender. It often occurs when someone's actions, behaviours, or identity deviate from societal or cultural and traditional expectations related to their assigned gender. Keep in mind that ideas about gender can vary widely across different cultures and communities, and what is considered a betrayal in one context may not be viewed the same way in another.
- **Global North, East, South, West** - How to refer to different groups of countries is often complicated and contains normative bias. During the Cold War, the first, second, and third world were used to define capitalist, communist and (post)colonies respectively. Developed and developing countries were then used in the years following the end of the Cold War. However, both of these framings imply a hierarchy that places colonisers at the top. In recent years, the terms global North, East, South and West have increasingly been used. These are not strict geographical distinctions, and no categorization is homogeneous but it can be a useful non-normative phrasing to talk about global trends. Global Majority and Global Minority are also frequently used, as well as periphery, semi-periphery, and core. For more definitions, check out our [REAL DEAL gender glossary](#)

- **Hegemonic masculinity** - in short, is a power structure - which you can compare with a pyramid. Where your gender, racialised identity, culture, religion and other identity factors determines your position in the pyramid. It makes assumptions about social expectations of what it means to be a “real man” and tends to prioritise traits such as strength, assertiveness, emotional resilience and dominance as superior to other traits. Hegemonic masculinity contributes to the reinforcement of traditional gender roles and can impact various aspects of social life, including relationships, work, and personal identity. It also upholds racism and colonialism.
- **Petro-masculinity** - intersection of misogyny/white patriarchal rule, fossil fuel systems and climate denial, and authoritarianism. Petro-masculinity is a reactionary masculinity: it "arises when agents of hegemonic masculinity feel threatened or undermined, thereby needing to inflate, exaggerate, or otherwise distort their traditional masculinity." Learn more: [Petro-masculinity: Fossil Fuels and Authoritarian Desire](#)
- **Postcolonialism** - “experience of colonialism and its past and present effects at the levels of material culture and of representation. Postcolonialism often involves the discussion of experiences such as those of slavery, migration, suppression and resistance, difference, race, gender, place and analysis of the responses to the discourses of imperial Europe, such as history, philosophy, anthropology and linguistics.” Learn more: [Routledge](#)
- **Queer ecology** - “Queering and intersectionalising ecological feminism means to no longer blame men and victimise women or to demonise culture and celebrate nature.” Source: Asmae Ourkiya’s foreword in: [Why the European Green Deal Needs Ecofeminism.](#) Learn more: [Climate Culture - What is Queer Ecology](#)
- **Regenerative societies** - “Going beyond sustainable societies, to societies that thrive and heal themselves.” Learn more: [regenerativesociety.org/defining-regenerative](#)
- **Toxic masculinity** - “points to a particular version of masculinity that is unhealthy for the men and boys [and others] who conform to it, and harmful for those around them. The phrase emphasises the worst aspects of stereotypically masculine attributes. Toxic masculinity is represented by qualities such as violence, dominance, emotional illiteracy, sexual entitlement, and hostility to femininity.” Learn more: [The Conversation](#)
- **Wellbeing economy** - “ an economy designed to serve people and the planet, not the other way around. Rather than treating economic growth as an end in and of itself and pursuing it at all costs, a Wellbeing Economy puts our human and planetary needs at the centre of its activities, ensuring that these needs are all equally met, by default.” Learn more: [weall.org/what-is-wellbeing-economy](#)

